

Zurich, Switzerland

Concept Summary: Total synthesis and SAR studies on modified benzylpenicillin

Author: Dr. Yuriy Lipisa

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***Note:** This document summarizes an original chemical concept under development and serves as a timestamp of authorship for a novel conceptual framework under active development. Specific mechanistic, structural, and biological details have been intentionally omitted and will be disclosed upon further experimental validation.*

Introduction and significance

Benzylpenicillin (penicillin G), the prototypical β -lactam antibiotic and often referred to as the "wonder drug," was first isolated by Alexander Fleming in 1928.¹ This discovery marked the inception of the golden era of β -lactam antibiotic therapy. However, bacterial resistance emerged rapidly: by 1940, penicillin-inactivating activity had been identified in *Escherichia coli* extracts, and by 1946, 14% of *Staphylococcus aureus* strains from Hammersmith Hospital displayed resistance to benzylpenicillin — a figure that rose to 80% by 1961.²

The subsequent escalation in antimicrobial resistance (AMR) can be attributed not only to the intrinsic adaptability of bacterial populations exposed to selective pressure but also to the widespread misuse and overuse of antibiotics across clinical, veterinary, and agricultural settings.² Compounding the problem is the reduced industrial investment in antibiotic research since the 1990s, largely due to the comparatively low return on investment.³ Bacterial resistance to β -lactam antibiotics involves several well-documented mechanisms, including modification of antibiotic target sites, reduced membrane permeability, efflux pump activation, and enzymatic degradation via β -lactamases.⁵ Despite continued innovation in β -lactam antibiotic development — including multiple generations of cephalosporins and the introduction of β -lactamase inhibitors such as tazobactam — the clinical threat posed by resistant strains remains high.⁴

Of particular concern is the flexible nature of β -lactamases as well as the emergence of metallo- β -lactamases, which develop broad antibiotic resistance profiles and are capable of hydrolyzing even advanced β -lactam analogues.⁶

For instance, the β -lactamase inhibitor avibactam has shown substantial activity in combination with ceftazidime, but resistance has already been reported when combined with other β -lactams such as ampicillin.⁷

This underscores the propensity of bacteria to evolve resistance even against next-generation inhibitors and highlights the pressing need for continued innovation in antibiotic design. While β -lactam antibiotics and their inhibitors remain indispensable in clinical practice, their long-term utility is threatened by ongoing evolution of resistance mechanisms — including mutations in penicillin-binding proteins (PBPs) and the proliferation of increasingly efficient β -lactamases.⁸

The U.S. Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC) has identified antimicrobial resistance as a critical global health threat.⁹

According to a 2024 CDC report, infection rates from resistant strains at healthcare settings in 2022 have increased substantially compared 2019 levels.¹⁰ Even in countries with stringent stewardship policies, such as Switzerland, the complete eradication of AMR remains

elusive.¹¹ A growing, albeit still limited, number of resistant infections continues to be reported, as illustrated in surveillance data from the Swiss Centre for Antibiotic Resistance (Figure 1).

In response to this global crisis, multiple international initiatives have been launched to stimulate antibiotic discovery. The 10×20 Initiative, for instance, aimed to bring ten new antibiotics to market by 2020.¹² Although 16 novel agents have since been approved, the rise of multidrug-resistant bacterial pathogens continues to demand new strategies and sustained research efforts.¹³

Figure 1. Selection of resistance rates of highly resistant micro-organisms in Switzerland (source: anresis.ch; Illustration: Communication in Science)

General Concept

The present research aims to explore the structural fine-tuning of β -lactam scaffolds to develop novel derivatives with improved resistance to enzymatic degradation while retaining antibacterial efficacy. Although predictive modeling of β -lactamase activity and bacterial cell permeability remains limited, meaningful advances can be achieved through systematic structure–activity relationship (SAR) studies.

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